

ADMAIORA

Grant Agreement number: 814413

Project acronym: ADMAIORA

Project title: ADvanced nanocomposite MAterIals fOr in situ treatment and
ultrASound-mediated management of osteoarthritis

Funding scheme: H2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2018-2020

D1.1

Report of the project management handbook

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Start date of project: 01/01/2019

Duration: 49 months

Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable: [SSSA]

Deliverable author: [Leonardo Ricotti, Beatrice Granvillano, Monica Giagheddu, Federica Radici, Daniela Parra, Denise Amram]

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PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Service)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Service)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Service)	

Document History

Version	Date	Author	Summary of Main Changes
1	15/03/2019	Leonardo Ricotti, SSSA	First version of the template for project Deliverables
2	10/04/2019	Leonardo Ricotti, SSSA	First complete version of the Deliverable
3	15/04/2019	Beatrice Granvillano, Monica Giagheddu, Federica Radici, Denise Amram, SSSA	Integrations to the Deliverable
4	18/04/2019	Leonardo Ricotti, SSSA	Document sent to the Consortium for a check
5	28/04/2019	Leonardo Ricotti, SSSA	Final version of the Deliverable
6	30/04/2019	Leonardo Ricotti, SSSA	Deliverable submission

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Executive summary

The ADMAIORA Management Handbook contains the instructions concerning the project procedures and other useful information to be used during the project lifetime.

The Handbook includes: (1) official information about the project contract and annexes, (2) the description of the project organisation (governance structure, project coordinator, project managers, board of partners, etc.) and conflict management, (3) a summary of the tentative plan of meetings of the BoP and IPEC during the whole duration of the project, (4) a complete list of the institutions and persons involved in the ADMAIORA project, (5) a description of the project management procedures and tools used to share key documents, to provide support on financial and administrative issues, to prepare project Deliverables and periodic reports, to facilitate the communication among partners and to organise periodic meetings and videoconferences.

By means of this information the Handbook is intended as an aid to all project beneficiaries, but also as a useful management tool for the coordinating institution.

1 Introduction

ADMAIORA is a challenging collaborative research project. The achievement of the expected objectives requires commitment and organization from all project partners. This document contains the instructions concerning the project procedures and other useful information to be used during the project lifetime.

This handbook does not constitute a legally binding document; in case of discrepancies between the signed Grant Agreement/Consortium Agreement and the handbook, the first signed documents will prevail.

2 Contract

Grant agreement number: 814413

Project acronym: ADMAIORA

Project title: ADvanced nanocomposite MATerIals fOr in situ treatment and ultRASound-mediated management of osteoarthritis

Framework programme: Horizon 2020

Call: H2020-NMBP-TR-IND-2018

Topic: NMBP-22-2018 - Osteoarticular tissues regeneration

Type of Action: RIA

Start date: January 1, 2019

End date: January 31, 2023

Duration: 49 months

Grant Agreement based on the: H2020 General MGA — Multi - 5.0

Estimated Project Cost: € 5,397,480.00

Requested EU Contribution: €5,397,480.00

List of annexes to the Grant Agreement:

Annex 1 - Description of the action

Annex 2 - Estimated budget for the action

2a - Additional information on the estimated budget

Annex 3 - Accession Forms

Annex 4 - Model for the financial statements

Annex 5 - Model for the certificate on the financial statements

Annex 6 - Model for the certificate on the methodology

SSSA already distributed the European Commission pre-financing to all partners, as shown in Table 1.

no.	Beneficiary	TOTAL EC GRANT	Partner share	Pre-financing Distribution
1	SSSA	€ 1.071.500,00	19,85%	€ 517.891,67
2	BIU	€ 524.800,00	9,72%	€ 253.653,33
3	IOR	€ 1.112.500,00	20,61%	€ 537.708,33
4	REGENTIS	€ 609.250,00	11,29%	€ 294.470,83
5	IGT	€ 670.500,00	12,42%	€ 324.075,00
6	PLASMACHEM	€ 325.625,00	6,03%	€ 157.385,42
7	VIMEX	€ 506.375,00	9,38%	€ 244.747,92
8	H&DWIRELESS	€ 576.930,00	10,69%	€ 278.849,50
TOTAL		€ 5.397.480,00	100,00%	€ 2.608.782,00

Table 1: Pre-financing distributed by the Coordinator on the basis of the specific shares of each Beneficiary.

3 Project organisation

3.1 Governance structure

The project management structure is reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1: ADMAIORA management structure.

3.2 Project Coordinator (PC)

The ADMAIORA Project Coordinator (PC) is Prof. Leonardo Ricotti from Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna (SSSA). The PC is the only contact point between the European Commission (EC) and the ADMAIORA Consortium and will coordinate the different research and technological activities foreseen in the project. The PC is also responsible for the overall project strategy, as follows:

- Handling all communications with the EC;
- Synchronize and integrate the results achieved in the different research activities;
- Monitor all development plans for those activities, and facilitate synergies among them;
- Ensure a proper exchange of feedback between research, development and validation activities;
- Decide the strategies with respect to the outreach and exploitation of the Consortium, the Project and its major results.

3.3 Project Manager (PM)

The ADMAIORA Project Manager (PM) will be appointed soon by the PC. At the moment, Prof. Leonardo Ricotti from SSSA is the PM *ad interim*. The PM is responsible for all the activities concerning the contractual, organizational and work-related project issues. The main specific activities under the responsibilities of the PM are:

- Handling all the relationships with the BoP;
- Monitoring that the operational streams of activities are developed in a synchronized way;
- Ensuring that all project deliverables are available on time (partner coordination for production of deliverables, monitoring against milestones and objectives in the project);
- Producing management documentation (progress reports, final report, documentation for project reviews, project meeting minutes, etc.);
- Creating conditions necessary for successful collaboration, promoting equality and diversity in the Consortium;
- Ensuring the compatibility of project management tools in use at each of the Consortium members.

3.4 Technical Project Manager (TPM)

The ADMAIORA Technical Project Manager (TPM) is Lorenzo Vannozzi, from SSSA. The TPM provides support on the organization and coordination of the technical aspects of the project. The main specific activities under the responsibilities of the TPM are:

- Analyzing and updating the technical workflow of the different WPs and of the whole project;
- Monitoring that the streams of activities are developed in a synchronized way and are compatible (easy to integrate) from a technical viewpoint;
- Producing technical documentation (datasheets, operative technical documents, etc.);
- Ensuring the compatibility of project technical tools in use at each of the Consortium members.

3.5 Communication Manager (CM)

The ADMAIORA Communication Manager (CM) is Michele Nardini, from SSSA. The CM is responsible for the communication initiatives and will empower the efficacy of the dissemination activities. He will support the PC and PM in devising, organizing, and managing such initiatives towards stakeholders, and he is responsible to collect feedbacks for them. The CM is aware of the technical evolutions of the project, but featured a solid background in communication science and advertising.

3.6 Financial and Administrative Coordination (FAC)

The ADMAIORA Financial and Administrative Coordination (FAC) is led by Dr. Daniela Parra (who is assisted by Dr. Beatrice Granvillano, Dr. Monica Giagheddu and Dr. Federica Radici) from the Administrative staff of The BioRobotics Institute of SSSA. The FAC will be closely working with the PM in order to synchronize the contractual and administrative items with the accounting and financial issues. The main responsibilities of the FAC will be:

- Coordinate the financial relationships between project partners;
- Control that project activities are performed within budget constraints;
- Coordinate the preparation of project cost statements;
- Support project participants in the collection of the required financial data to be reported in each reporting period;
- Periodically control the consistency of presented data;
- Transfer of advance payments in time.

3.7 Board of Partners (BoP)

The PC will be supported in the scientific and technical management of the project by the Board of Partners (BoP). This organ participates in taking the main decisions during the project course. The BoP will include one person in charge for each project partner and will be chaired by the PC. Each partner has nominated its representative in the Consortium Agreement: this person has the authority to both represent and commit the respective organization in the project decision making or in case of conflicts (Table 2).

Partner	Representative	Number of votes
SSSA	Leonardo Ricotti	1
BIU	Gilbert Daniel Nessim	1
IOR	Gina Lisignoli	1
REGENTIS	Aharon Wechsler	1
IGT	Erik Dumont	1
PLASMACHEM	Carsten Jost	1
VIMEX	Tomasz Gapinski	1
HDW	Pär Bergsten	1
	Total	8

Table 2: List of partners' representatives and votes in the BoP.

The BoP will be in charge of setting the broad project direction so as to ensure that project execution will produce benefits to all partners. If a BoP member will not be present, neither represented at a management board meeting, that partner will be bound to honor decisions taken and actions placed on it in his/her absence.

The BoP is responsible to take the following decisions.

On content, finances, and intellectual property rights:

- To propose amendments to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Funding Authority;
- Changes to the Consortium Plan;
- Modifications to Attachment 1 (Background Included);
- Additions to Attachment 3 (List of Third Parties for simplified transfer according to Section 8.3.2);
- Additions to Attachment 4 (Identified Affiliated Entities).

On the evolution of the consortium:

- Possible entry of a new Party to the consortium and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party;
- Possible withdrawal of a Party from the consortium and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal;
- Identification of a breach of its obligations under this Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement by a Party;
- Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party;
- Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party;
- Exclusion of a Defaulting Party from the Consortium and related measures;
- Proposal to the Funding Authority for a change of the Coordinator;
- Proposal to the Funding Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project;
- Proposal to the Funding Authority for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement.

Appointments:

- End-Users Board members

The BoP shall meet periodically: once per year is required unless emergency situations will require early gather. The chairperson of the BoP shall convene ordinary meetings at least once per year and shall also convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any Member. In addition, regular communications among the members of the BoP will be based on e-mail, telephone, videoconference (e.g. Zoom or Skype). BoP meetings organisation and agenda setting, voting rules and quorum, veto rights, minutes preparation and timing, etc. are regulated by the Consortium Agreement.

3.8 Intellectual Property and Exploitation Committee (IPEC)

The ADMAIORA Intellectual Property and Exploitation Committee (IPEC) is chaired by REGENTIS and assisted by all the industrial partners, namely IGT, PLASMACHEM, VIMEX and HDW. SSSA is also part of the Committee as a link between the technical activities and the exploitation efforts. The IPEC is responsible for the Consortium Intellectual Property (IP)

protection, as ruled by the Consortium Agreement, and for the management and execution of the Exploitation Agreement between the Parties. In particular the IPEC:

- is involved in the exploitation task;
- manages the Consortium IP protection, in accordance with the obligations stated under the Consortium Agreement;
- gives indications about IP coverage, freedom to operate and market trends in the field;
- approves procedures, policies, and the plan on the use and dissemination of knowledge;
- defines the conditions under which the project partners interface, publish and make available to third parties the technologies derived from the project;
- assists the BoP in decisions concerning publications and granting of access rights: all scientific publications resulting from the project will be checked by the IPEC to protect the IP properly;
- will produce the Exploitation Roadmap at the end of the project.

Table 3 shows the IPEC representatives and the overall votes.

Partner	Representative	Number of votes
SSSA	Leonardo Ricotti	1
REGENTIS	Aharon Wechsler	1
IGT	Erik Dumont	1
PLASMACHEM	Carsten Jost	1
VIMEX	Tomasz Gapinski	1
HDW	Pär Bergsten	1
	Total	6

Table 3: List of representatives in the IPEC.

The IPEC meets physically at least once a year. In addition, regular communications among the members of the IPEC will be based on e-mail, telephone, videoconference (e.g. Zoom or Skype).

3.9 Work Package Leader (WPL) Board

The ADMAIORA project is organized into eight work packages (WPs). Each WP is led by a single partner (Work Package Leader - WPL) who assumes responsibilities for the timely implementation of the work planned in the respective work package and reports to the PC, PM and BoP. Each WPL is responsible for taking appropriate measures to make the WP activities perfectly synchronized and integrated with the results produced elsewhere in the project. The WP Leaders nominated Gina Lisignoli from the Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli (IOR) as Chairperson of the Board.

The WP Leaders Board:

- Produces and maintains the WPs project plan and resource allocation in collaboration with the PM, the TPM and the task leaders;
- Receives from the PC instructions for promoting and exploiting synergies with other projects and, when adequate and useful, is responsible for exchanging information and data on similar technical activities;

- Proposes and justifies to the BoP any change in the WPs composition in terms of effort and budget allocation as well as requests for adding/changing participants;
- Shall harmonize the work in the respective WPs and the overall architecture;
- The Chairperson of the Board coordinates the mentioned activities, collecting inputs and proposals from the WPLs and helping the PC and the PM to keep updated the status of each WP.

3.10 Ethical Advisory Board (EAB)

The Ethical Advisory Board (EAB) is composed of

- internal experts belonging to the Parties directly responsible to submit any approval requests to the competent Ethics, namely SSSA and IOR;
- external members, with a renowned experience in Ethics.

The PC is authorised to execute, on behalf of the whole Consortium, a non-disclosure agreement with each external member of the EAB. Its terms shall be not less strict than those stipulated within the Consortium Agreement, and it shall be concluded no later than 30 days after their nomination or before any confidential information will be exchanged, whichever date is earlier.

The EAB will nominate a Chair among its members.

The EAB will ensure adherence to ethical principles during the project lifetime. The EAB is directly responsible to submit any approval requests to the competent Ethics Committees before performing the project experiments.

In particular, the EAB:

- monitors the implementation of activities, ensuring adherence to ethical principles and will advise the PC, the PTM, and PM on ethical issues arising in the project;
- gives prior approval to RTD activities and experiments requiring ethical approvals;
- explores the socio-ethical sensitive aspects of the study, addresses the public concerns about research, and studies the possible consequences in terms of benefits and possible risks;
- organizes ethical reviews during the project lifetime, if needed, and ensures the follow-up of the evaluations.

The Chairperson shall write the minutes of the EAB meetings and prepare the implementation of the EAB's suggestions. The EAB members shall be allowed to participate in Board of Partners meetings upon invitation but have not any voting rights.

3.11 External Scientific Board (ESB)

The External Scientific Board (ESB) is composed of academic experts in the fields of orthopedics, nanotechnology, nanotoxicology, materials science, medical devices and ultrasound technologies. A representative of health legislation will be also included.

The Coordinator is authorised to execute, on behalf of the whole Consortium, a non-disclosure agreement with each external member of the ESB. Its terms shall be not less strict than those stipulated in the Consortium Agreement, and it shall be concluded no later than 30 days after their nomination or before any confidential information will be exchanged, whichever date is earlier.

The ESB aims at advising the BoP and the WPL Board in the project course about the most appropriate scientific and technical decisions to be taken for achieving the final project objectives. The ESB members are expected to participate in selected ADMAIORA meetings upon invitation.

3.12 End-Users Board (EUB)

The End-Users Board (EUB) includes end-users along the whole value chain (*e.g.* patients affected by oostoarthritis, surgeons, sports representatives, policy makers, etc.). End-users will be reached, among the different channels, also through associations that already guaranteed their support to the ADMAIORA project, namely:

- SIGASCOT (The Italian Knee Society Arthroscopy Sport Cartilage Orthopedic Technologies) – President: Prof. Pietro Randelli;
- ESCEO (European Society for Clinical and Economic Aspects of Osteoporosis, Osteoarthritis and Musculoskeletal Diseases) – President: M.D. Jean-Yves Reginster;
- AMRER (Association of Rheumatic Patients of Emilia Romagna) – President: Ms. Guerrina Filippi

Further possible members could be identified and appointed by the BoP.

The Coordinator is authorised to execute, on behalf of the whole Consortium, a non-disclosure agreement with each external member of the EUB. Its terms shall be not less stringent than those stipulated in the Consortium Agreement, and it shall be concluded no later than 30 days after their nomination or before any confidential information will be exchanged, whichever date is earlier.

The EUB will favor the dissemination and communication of the project results, making easy contacts outside the Consortium with appropriate target groups. In addition, the EUB will also help in recruiting volunteers for the project validation phase. They are expected to participate in selected ADMAIORA meetings, upon invitation, and to be involved in specific project activities.

4 Conflict management

In case of disputes arising in the Consortium, including cases of abuse of powers, which cannot be amicably solved, the partners will follow the procedures specified in the Consortium Agreement, art. 11.8 (Settlement of disputes).

5 Plan for the project meetings

Figure 2 shows a tentative plan of meetings of the BoP and IPEC during the whole duration of the project. These meetings will be held in correspondence to some technical and medical meetings, thus to exploit at best the presence of all partners. Each partner will host one meeting. The exact dates of the meetings will be decided by using the free on-line service www.doodle.com. The PM will invite the participants to vote and choose the selected dates depending on their availabilities.

Location	M2 (Feb 19)	M9 (Sep 19)	M15 (Mar 20)	M20 (Ago 20)	M27 (Mar 21)	M33 (Sep 21)	M38 (Feb 22)	M43 (Jul 22)
SSSA (Pontedera, Italy)	KoM IPEC							
BIU (Ramat Gan, Israel)		T&M BoP						
IOR (Bologna, Italy)			T&M IPEC					
REGENTIS (Tel-Aviv, Israel)						T&M BoP		
IGT (Pessac, France)					T&M IPEC			
PLASMACHEM (Berlin, Germany)							T&M BoP	
VIMEX (Gliwice, Poland)								T&M IPEC
HDW (Kista, Sweden)				T&M BoP				

Figure 2: Tentative plan of ADMAIORA project meetings. KoM = Kick-Off meeting. T&M = Technical and Medical meeting. BoP = Meeting of the Board of Partners. IPEC = Meeting of the Intellectual Property and Exploitation Committee.

6 Participants and contacts

The up to date list of the ADMAIORA participants and contacts is reported in Table 4.

#	Institution	Short name	Person	e-mail address	Role in ADMAIORA
1	Scuola Superiore Sant'Anna	SSSA	Leonardo Ricotti	leonardo.ricotti@santannapisa.it	Project Coordinator and PI for SSSA
			Lorenzo Vannozzi	lorenzo.vannozzi@santannapisa.it	Technical Project Manager
			Michele Nardini	michele.nardini@santannapisa.it	Communication Manager
			Federica Iberite	federica.iberite@santannapisa.it	Scientific staff
			Francesco Fontana	francesco.fontana@santannapisa.it	Scientific staff
			Andrea Cafarelli	andrea.cafarelli@santannapisa.it	Scientific staff
			Andrea Aliperta	andrea.aliperta@gmail.com	Communication staff
			Denise Amram	denise.amram@santannapisa.it	Data Protection Officer

			Daniela Parra	daniela.parra@santannapisa.it	Financial and Administrative staff
			Beatrice Granvillano	beatrice.granvillano@santannapisa.it	Financial and Administrative staff
			Monica Giagheddu	monica.giagheddu@santannapisa.it	Financial and Administrative staff
			Federica Radici	federica.radici@santannapisa.it	Financial and Administrative staff
2	Bar Ilan University	BIU	Gilbert Daniel Nessim	gdnessim@biu.ac.il	PI for BIU
			Madina Telkhozhayeva	telkhozhayeva@gmail.com	Scientific staff
			Eti Teblum	eti.teblum@gmail.com	Scientific staff
			Estelle Waise	estelle.waise@biu.ac.il	Financial and Administrative staff
3	Istituto Ortopedico Rizzoli	IOR	Gina Lisignoli	gina.lisignoli@ior.it	PI for IOR and Chair of the WPL Board
			Lia Pulsatelli	lia.pulsatelli@ior.it	Scientific staff
			Riccardo Meliconi	riccardo.meliconi@ior.it	Scientific staff
			Milena Fini	milena.fini@ior.it	Scientific staff
			Alessandro Russo	a.russo@biomec.ior.it	Scientific staff
			Cristina Manferdini	cristina.manferdini@ior.it	Scientific staff
			Elena Gabusi	elena.gabusi@ior.it	Scientific staff
			Matilde Tschon	matilde.tschon@ior.it	Scientific staff
			Diego Trucco	diego.trucco@ior.it	Scientific staff
			Olga Addimanda	olga.addimanda@ior.it	Scientific staff
			Stefano Zaffagnini	stefano.zaffagnini@ior.it	Scientific staff
			Andrea Rizzi	andrea.rizzi@ior.it	Financial and Administrative staff

4	Regentis Biomaterials Ltd.	REGENTIS	Aharon Wechsler	Roni@regentis.co.il	PI for REGENTIS and Chair of the IPEC
			Alastair Clemow	aclemow@regentis.co.il	Scientific staff
			Nira Yakoboviz	nira@regentis.co.il	Financial and Administrative staff
			Livnat Ben-Zur	livnat@regentis.co.il	Scientific and business staff
5	Image Guided Therapy SA	IGT	Erik Dumont	erik.dumont@imageguidedtherapy.com	PI for IGT
6	PlasmaChem Produktions und Handel GmbH	PLASMACHEM	Carsten Jost	c.jost@plasmachem.com	PI for PLASMACHEM
			Yirij Fedutik	fedutik@plasmachem.com	Scientific staff
7	Vimex Endoscopy	VIMEX	Tomasz Gapinski	tgapinski@vimex.eu	PI for VIMEX
			Krzysztof Lenartowicz	klenartowicz@vimex.eu	Scientific staff
			Paulina Galas	pgalas@vimex.eu	Scientific staff
			Małgorzata Gonsior	mgonsior@vimex.eu	Project management
8	H&D Wireless AB	HDW	Pär Bergsten	par.bergsten@hd-wireless.se	PI for HDW
			Åke Jernberger	ake.jernberger@hd-wireless.se	Scientific staff
			Per-Olov Östberg	perolov.ostberg@hd-wireless.se	Financial and Administrative staff
			Magnus Eriksson	magnus.eriksson@hd-wireless.se	Project Management
			Frida Nordeman	frida.nordeman@hd-wireless.se	Communication staff

Table 4: List of participating institutions, persons, email addresses and roles in the ADMAIORA project.

7 Management: procedures and tools

The Project Coordinator has agreed with the partners, during the kick-off meeting, a series of procedures and tools to be used in order to make the overall project management and

coordination smooth and effective. Such procedures and tools concern: (1) sharing of project documents; (2) support on financial and administrative issues; (3) preparation of project Deliverables and periodic reports; (4) communication and meeting organisation between partners.

7.1 Sharing of documents

The ADMAIORA partners decided to create and use one Dropbox shared folder with few folders inside, to quickly find key documents/information and to effectively collaborate on the update of some documents, such as:

- ADMAIORA project key information and documents;
- Administrative documents and FAQs;
- Communication and dissemination activities;
- Consortium Agreement;
- Deliverables;
- Partners contacts;
- Minutes of the meetings;
- Important papers and patents, dealing with the project objectives;
- Templates;
- Brochures;
- Other operative documents requiring the contribution of different partners and/or used by all partners.

Figure 3 shows the structure of the above-mentioned folder, with all its sub-folders.

-
- ✓ ADMAIORA project key information and documents
 - ✓ Administrative documents and FAQs
 - ✓ Communication activities
 - ✓ Consortium Agreement
 - ✓ Deliverables
 - ✓ Dissemination activities
 - ✓ Open Access Research Data
 - ✓ Papers and patents produced by the Consortium
 - ✓ Partners contacts
 - ✓ Project meetings
 - ✓ Project shared calls
 - ✓ Relevant papers
 - ✓ Relevant patents
 - ✓ Templates

Figure 3: Structure of the ADMAIORA folder, shared among all partners.

It is worth mentioning that data will be exclusively collected and stored on servers sited in EU, as specified in the SSSA's Dropbox Business account Terms & Conditions. This ensures that shared folders are managed through organizational and technical measures which are fully compliant with the current EU legislation on General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) Reg. EU/2016/679. Moreover, whether the folder includes personal data, the related access

will be allowed only to instructed, therefore authorized, members of each partner involved in the specific activity. Further appropriate measures will be implemented to process possible sensitive data emerging during the project implementation. These folders will be shared for all the duration of the project including the review process, then they will be stored by each partner following the conditions required by the law.

7.2 Support on financial and administrative issues

The Project Coordinator and the FAC devised a series of measures to support the project partners in administrative and financial issues. They created a dedicated folder on Dropbox, in the shared project folder (see section 8.1), named "Administrative documents and FAQs". Here, the following documents have been uploaded:

- Annotated Model Grant Agreement (AGMA): http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/amga/h2020-amga_en.pdf;
- "Model Grant Agreement – Financial Issues" document;
- H2020 Online Manual: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/index_en.htm;
- "Avoiding Common Financial Errors" document, by Vittorio Morelli (Deputy Head of the CAS - Common Audit Service);
- "Report and payment – in practice" document;
- "Administrative and financial FAQs"

The Administrative and financial FAQs is a living document, continuously updated by the FAC members, in which questions and practical issues raised by the partners are reported, with the correspondent answers and correct workflow to be followed. This will facilitate the partners in choosing the right direction for their administrative/financial choices and will avoid to duplicate the FAC efforts: the document should avoid to repeat the same information several times to the different partners, separately.

7.3 Preparation of project Deliverables and periodic reports

During the project course, the partners have to deal with periodic reports and with project Deliverables and to carefully respect their timings.

Concerning periodic reports, the project Action is divided into the following reporting periods (RP):

RP1: from M1 to M19 (1st January 2019 – 31th July 2020)

RP2: from month 20 to month 37 (1st August 2020 – 31th January 2022)

RP3: from month 38 to month 49 (1st February 2022 – 31th January 2023)

The Coordinator must submit to the EC a periodic report within 60 days following the end of each RP (it could slightly earlier, depending on the review meeting schedule). SSSA will require to the partners all the needed scientific and administrative documents in due time without delays, in order to timely submit them to the EC.

Deliverables are listed in the Annex I. The complete Deliverable list with all details is reported in Table 5.

WP No	Del Rel. No	Title	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Nature	Dissemination Level	Est. Del. Date
WP1	D1.1	Project management handbook	Report of the project management handbook	SSSA	Report	Public	30 Apr 2019
WP1	D1.2	6 months activity report	Report of the project activities during the first 6 months	SSSA	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jul 2019
WP2	D2.1	Technological specifications	Report of the technological specifications required for achieving the objectives established in the ADMAIORA project	SSSA	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 May 2019
WP2	D2.2	Clinical/biological specifications	Report of the clinical and biological specifications required for achieving the objectives established in the ADMAIORA project	IOR	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 May 2019
WP3	D3.1	PEG-fibrinogen based hydrogel prototype development	Demonstration of PEG-fibrinogen based hydrogel prototypes	REGENTIS	Demonstrator	Public	29 Feb 2020
WP3	D3.2	Pluronic-fibrinogen based hydrogel prototype development	Demonstration of Pluronic-fibrinogen based hydrogel prototypes	REGENTIS	Demonstrator	Public	29 Feb 2020
WP3	D3.3	Report on carbon-based nanofillers	Report on carbon-based nanofillers, detailed with chemical structures and technical diagrams on nanoparticle properties	BIU	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Aug 2020
WP3	D3.4	Report on piezoelectric nanofillers	Report on piezoelectric nanofillers, detailed with chemical structures and technical diagrams on nanoparticle properties	PLASMACHEM	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Aug 2020
WP3	D3.5	Intermediate results on nanocomposite hydrogels	Report on intermediate results on nanocomposite hydrogels	REGENTIS	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2021
WP3	D3.6	Nanocomposite hydrogels prototypes	Demonstration of the final nanocomposite hydrogel prototypes	REGENTIS	Demonstrator	Public	31 Jan 2022
WP4	D4.1	Selected components for the innovative LIPUS stimulation set-ups	Selection of the components for the innovative LIPUS stimulation set-ups, and report of their technical datasheets	SSSA	Other	Public	30 Sep 2019

WP4	D4.2	Assembled innovative LIPUS stimulation set-ups	Demonstration of the assembled innovative LIPUS stimulation set-ups, and prototype testing	SSSA	Demonstrator	Public	29 Feb 2020
WP4	D4.3	Preliminary in vitro validation of LIPUS stimulation on cells	Report on preliminary in vitro results of LIPUS stimulation on cells	SSSA	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	29 Feb 2020
WP4	D4.4	Intermediate models and FEM simulations	Report on intermediate models and FEM simulations	IGT	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2021
WP4	D4.5	Report on technologies for in vivo translation of LIPUS	Report on technologies for in vivo translation of LIPUS	IGT	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2022
WP5	D5.1	Preliminary software structure	Demonstrator of a preliminary software structure	H&D Wireless	Demonstrator	Public	30 Nov 2019
WP5	D5.2	Preliminary brace skeleton	Demonstration of a preliminary brace skeleton prototype	IGT	Demonstrator	Public	30 Nov 2019
WP5	D5.3	Preliminary foot-controlled pneumatic flow for bioprinting	Demonstration of a preliminary foot-controlled pneumatic system prototype for bioprinting	VIMEX	Demonstrator	Public	30 Nov 2019
WP5	D5.4	Intermediate wireless communication and IoT technologies	Report on wireless communication and IoT technologies at an intermediate stage	H&D Wireless	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Aug 2020
WP5	D5.5	Intermediate bioprinting handheld system	Report on the bioprinting handheld system at an intermediate stage	VIMEX	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Aug 2020
WP5	D5.6	Intermediate stimulation/monitoring brace	Report on the stimulation/monitoring brace at an intermediate stage	IGT	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Aug 2020
WP5	D5.7	Final wireless communication and IoT technologies	Final report on the wireless communication and IoT technologies, and demonstration of the communication flow	H&D Wireless	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2022

WP5	D5.8	Final bioprinting handheld system	Final report on the bioprinting handheld system, and demonstration of the prototype	VIMEX	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2022
WP5	D5.9	Final stimulation/monitoring brace	Final report on the stimulation/monitoring brace, and demonstration of the prototype	IGT	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2022
WP5	D5.10	Report on technology integration	Demonstration of technology integration, and planning of the protocols for final validation tests	SSSA	Demonstrator	Public	31 Jul 2022
WP6	D6.1	Preliminary results of in vitro tests - cytotoxicity	Report on preliminary results of in vitro tests - cytotoxicity	IOR	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2021
WP6	D6.2	Preliminary results of in vitro tests - LIPUS-triggered bioeffects	Report on preliminary results of in vitro tests - LIPUS-triggered bioeffects	IOR	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2021
WP6	D6.3	Ethics approval for efficacy in vivo trials and usability tests on human volunteers	Report on the Ethics approval for efficacy in vivo trials and usability tests on human volunteers	IOR	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jul 2021
WP6	D6.4	Final results of in vitro tests - cytotoxicity	Final report on the results of in vitro tests - cytotoxicity	IOR	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2022
WP6	D6.5	Final results of in vitro tests - LIPUS-triggered bioeffects	Final report on the results of in vitro tests - LIPUS-triggered bioeffects	IOR	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2022
WP6	D6.6	Report on ISO 10993 biocompatibility	Report on ISO 10993 biocompatibility	IOR	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jul 2022
WP6	D6.7	Results of therapeutic efficacy validation tests on male and	Report on the results of therapeutic efficacy validation tests on male	IOR	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	31 Jan 2023

		female rabbit model of OA	and female rabbit model of OA			(including the Commission Services)	
WP6	D6.8	Results of therapeutic efficacy pilot study on sheep model of OA	Report on the results of therapeutic efficacy pilot study on sheep model of OA	IOR	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2023
WP6	D6.9	Results of usability tests on human volunteers	Report on the results of usability tests on human volunteers	SSSA	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2023
WP7	D7.1	Project website	Presentation of the project website	SSSA	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	31 Mar 2019
WP7	D7.2	Preliminary dissemination, communication and exploitation plan	Preliminary report of the preliminary dissemination, communication and exploitation plan	BIU	Report	Public	30 Apr 2019
WP7	D7.3	1st IP report and Consortium freedom to operate	1st IP report and Consortium freedom to operate analysis	REGENTIS	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 May 2019
WP7	D7.4	Initial data management plan	Report on initial data management plan	BIU	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	Public	31 Jul 2019
WP7	D7.5	Patent filing on the key elements of the ADMAIORA approach	Patent filing analysis on the key elements of the ADMAIORA approach	REGENTIS	Websites, patents filling, etc.	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2020
WP7	D7.6	Report on 1st ADMAIORA workshop	Report on 1st ADMAIORA workshop	SSSA	Report	Public	31 Jan 2020
WP7	D7.7	Intermediate data management and innovation management	Intermediate report on data management and innovation management	BIU	ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot	Public	31 Jan 2021
WP7	D7.8	Report on 2nd ADMAIORA workshop and other key communication events	Report on 2nd ADMAIORA workshop and other key communication events	SSSA	Report	Public	31 Jan 2021
WP7	D7.9	2nd IP report	2nd IP report	REGENTIS	Report	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jan 2022
WP7	D7.10	Report on 3rd ADMAIORA workshop	Report on 3rd ADMAIORA workshop	SSSA	Report	Public	31 Jan 2022
WP7	D7.11	Final Exploitation Roadmap and business plans,	Report on the final Exploitation Roadmap and business plans,	REGENTIS	Report	Confidential, only for members of the	31 Jan 2023

		management plan and dissemination activities	management plan and dissemination activities			consortium (including the Commission Services)	
WP7	D7.12	Final innovation management, 4th ADMAIORA workshop and other communication activities	Final report on the innovation management, 4th ADMAIORA workshop and other communication activities	SSSA	Report	Public	31 Jan 2023
WP8	D8.1	H - Requirement No. 5	Preliminary documents demonstrating compliance to ethical issues, concerning identification/recruitment of research participants, informed consent procedures, templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets, vulnerable individuals/groups, physical procedures to be used, incidental findings policy opinions/approvals by ethics committees and/or competent authorities for the research with humans, if available.	SSSA	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jul 2019
WP8	D8.2	A - Requirement No. 6	Preliminary documents demonstrating compliance to ethical issues, concerning animal experiments.	SSSA	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Jul 2019
WP8	D8.3	A - Requirement No. 7	Final documents demonstrating compliance to ethical issues, concerning in vivo biocompatibility and efficacy tests approved by the relevant Ethical committees and authorization bodies.	SSSA	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	30 Apr 2022
WP8	D8.4	H - Requirement No. 8	Final documents demonstrating compliance to ethical issues, concerning tests on human subjects, approved by the relevant Ethical committees and authorization bodies.	SSSA	Ethics	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	31 Aug 2022

Table 5: Complete list of ADMAIORA Deliverables, with description, type, Lead Beneficiary, confidentiality level and due date.

The following strategy has been agreed between the partners, for managing the project Deliverables:

- All Deliverables preparatory documents are available in “Deliverables” shared folder on Dropbox (the sub-folder names indicate the Deliverable number, the Lead Beneficiary and the due date. For example: D1.1_SSSA_30_04_2019, D2.2_IOR_31_05_2019, etc.);
- Within such sub-folders, a Deliverable template is available;

For each Deliverable:

- 45 days before the deadline, the Project Coordinator sends a reminder to the partner responsible for the deliverable, attaching a pre-elaborated template and few lines with general indications. The responsible starts to work on the document and asks contributions to the other partners involved;
- 25 days before the deadline: the partner responsible for the deliverable sends to the Project Coordinator a 1st complete draft of the document;
- 20 days before the deadline: the Coordinator sends a feedback, possibly asking for revisions/integrations;
- 10 days before the deadline: the partner responsible for the deliverable sends to the Coordinator a 2nd revised and final draft of the document;
- At the deadline: the Deliverable is submitted by the Coordinator.

A similar procedure will be used to prepare the periodic reports. The overall procedure can be facilitated by a project management tool, Trello, which will be used by SSSA in order to schedule deadlines and tasks without disclosing any confidential information.

7.4 Communication and meeting organisation

During the kick-off meeting, the partners agreed to create the following mailing lists, managed by SSSA, in order to facilitate communications:

- consortium@admaiora-project.com – it includes all the people involved in the project and reported in Table 4;
- Principal-Investigators@admaiora-project.com – it includes the PIs of the different partners involved in the project.

Further mailing lists will be created in the project course, depending on the specific needs that will arise.

In addition to the official physical project meetings, shown in Figure 2, additional and frequent interactions between the partners will be needed, to carefully monitor the advancement of project activities and to smoothly coordinate the partners’ efforts. The partners agreed to set periodical short plenary meetings (at least the PIs and Project Managers of each unit) every 2/3 weeks. This will allow to quickly update on the work done, on possible issues/deviations from the plans and to set new intermediate micro-tasks, useful to progress in an aligned way. The exact dates of these meetings will be decided by using the free on-line service www.doodle.com. The PM will invite the participants to vote and choose the selected dates depending on their availabilities. The tool identified for such meetings is Zoom, a freely available video/web conferencing tool (<https://zoom.us/>). SSSA purchased a professional account and will organize the shared calls. Zoom was chosen due to the impossibility of some SMEs involved in the Consortium to use Skype. In addition, whenever needed, the Project Coordinator will also organize one-to-one calls with the single partners (by using Zoom, Skype or phone) to discuss technical and organizational issues.

8 Conclusions

The Project Management Handbook is an important guideline and a useful shared source of key information for the ADMAIORA partners.

It describes the agreed management structure, highlighting the related governance, tasks, roles, and procedures. Furthermore, it illustrates all the tools used by the coordinator and the managers to effectively monitor and steer the project activities, which are properly summarized.

It also takes the opportunity to clarify possible matters arising from the grant agreement and its annexes.

In conclusion, it provides those practical information that shall be referred to throughout the project life, guiding partners within all the ADMAIORA administrative documents and all the Management decisions took at the very first stage of the project.